

Environmental Research

Variability of Traffic Noise Pollution Levels as a Function of City Size Variables

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	ER-21-788R1
Article Type:	Research paper
Section/Category:	Environmental Health & Risk Assessment
Keywords:	Environmental Pollution; Urban planning; Road traffic noise; road categorisation method; environmental management
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First Author:	Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas, PhD
Order of Authors:	Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas, PhD Guillermo Rey Gozalo, PhD David Montes-González, PhD Rosendo Vílchez-Gomez, PhD Valentín Gómez Escobar, PhD
Abstract:	Noise levels measured in 27 cities with different areas (from 0.6 km ² to 59.27 km ²) and populations (from approximately 2,000 to 70,000 inhabitants) were compared with respect to five different urban characteristics (population, area, total street length, density, and linear density). Comparisons were conducted for both overall city noise levels and noise registered on five types of roads with different functionality using the Categorisation Method. The results showed that four of the five cities' characteristics presented a significant correlation with the noise levels (all except for density). The calculated correlations were better for noise levels in the different categories than the overall noise values, with higher explained variability on the streets with more traffic. Therefore, the road categorisation method can be used not only to assess the noise variations within cities, but also to better explain the effect of noise on the analysed city characteristics. The results of the calculated relationships enable the estimation of noise levels both currently and in future urban developments of noise values on different types of streets.
Response to Reviewers:	<p>The authors would like to thank the reviewers for their comments and suggestions, which have helped to improve the quality of the manuscript.</p> <p>Reviewer #1</p> <p>Dear authors, A nice article draft, my comments are minor.</p> <p>1. "Categorization method" is very general when used in keywords, abstracts and such. Perhaps "road categorization method" is better?</p> <p>Response to Reviewer #1 comment No. 1: The reviewer's suggestion has been considered and the "road categorisation method" has been used in the abstract and keywords. The authors have used capital letters (Categorisation Method) in the other sections of the article because this method was designed by the authors and analysed in previous studies.</p> <p>2. Linear density is a very interesting measure, and as you I don't think it has been analyzed previously, at least not for road traffic noise.</p> <p>Response to Reviewer #1 comment No. 2: We agree with the reviewer that linear population density is an interesting variable that has a significant relationship with road traffic noise. Some previous studies have analysed the relationship between road</p>

surface density and noise levels (Salomons and Pont, 2012). However, we are not aware that linear population density has been used in urban noise studies. This variable may be of interest from an urban planning point of view as the frequency of use of urban roads is related to the resident population and the availability of roads.

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I have few suggestions and minor concerns.

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Comments

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Manuscript number: ER-21-788

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2. There is no page numbering and line numberings

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include page numbering. Line numbering has not been added to the manuscript because the authors' guide states: "Please do not include line numbering as this is automatically imposed by the editorial system".

3. Keywords: Health should be removed from keywords

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Response to Reviewer #3 comment No. 4: These sentences have been modified taking into account the reviewer's suggestions. The new sentences are shown below: "The objective of this study is to analyse the capacity of variables related to the size of cities to explain noise levels on their streets. Categorisation Method has been used to stratify the city streets (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005; Rey Gozalo et al., 2012, 2013a; Romeu et al., 2011). As this method classifies streets according to their functionality, this study allows to analyse the relationships between urban noise and variables related to the size of the city taking into account the mobility of people. Two widely used variables have been used (population and area) and a new variable less used for this purpose has been added (streets length)."

5. Methodology: Provide reference for the following sentence, "According to the previous studies for this size range of cities, approximately 10 points are sufficient to obtain a representative sample of the sound level in each category

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7. Results and discussion: The word shown used for the tables shall be revised to " as given in", The slope and intercept coefficients, the coefficient of determination (R²), and the standard error of the regression lines are shown in Table 2

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"At the beginning of the measurements, each city's streets were classified in the five categories defined above in the road categorisation method. Therefore, all streets were classified according to their functionality in all studied cities. Figure 1 (b) shows the stratification of the streets in Valdivia (Chile)."

14. It was mentioned that 10 points were selected but did not explain that how many from each country were selected (Approx. this make 3 roads from each country)

Response to Reviewer #3 comment No. 14: The authors apologise if the methodology was not explained clearly enough. They have modified some sentences in this new version to clarify that 10 points were selected for each category in each of the cities studied and included in Table 1.

"A random selection of measurement points in each of these road categories was then carried out. According to the previous studies for this size range of cities, approximately 10 points are sufficient to obtain a representative sample of the sound level in each category (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005, Carmona del Río et al., 2011; Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a). These studies have also shown that this number does not depend on the size of the city and the category considered. About 50 points were thus sampled in each city."

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Guillermo Rey Gozalo
INTERRA/Dpto. Física Aplicada/Universidad de Extremadura
Avda. Universidad s/n, 10003 Cáceres, SPAIN
guille@unex.es

Cáceres, 5th May 2021

Dear Editor José L. Domingo:

Please find enclosed a revised version of our paper "Variability of Traffic Noise Pollution Levels as a Function of City Size Variables" (No.: ER-21-788) which we are interested in publishing in the *Environmental Research* journal.

The authors are grateful to the reviewer for his/her valuable comments. We have included in this new version of the paper some modifications in accordance with the reviewer's comments.

Yours sincerely,

Guillermo Rey Gozalo

The authors would like to thank the reviewers for their comments and suggestions, which have helped to improve the quality of the manuscript.

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Highlights

- The categorisation method and city size variables explain most of urban noise
- Linear models predict urban traffic noise with standard errors lower than 2.2 dBA
- City size variables explains the noise variability in road categories by up to 86%
- Linear density explains noise variability statistically similar to size variables
- Surface population density is a poor descriptor of urban noise variability

**Variability of Traffic Noise Pollution Levels ~~in Urban Environments~~ as a Function
of ~~Some of the Main~~ City Size Variables Characteristics**

Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas,^a Guillermo Rey Gozalo,^{a,b,*} David Montes-González,^{a,c}

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^aINTERRA, Lambda, Departamento de Física Aplicada, Universidad de Extremadura,
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ABSTRACT

Noise levels measured in 27 cities with different areas (from 0.6 km² to 59.27 km²) and populations (from approximately 2,000 to 70,000 inhabitants) were compared with respect to five different urban characteristics (population, area, total street length, density, and linear density). Comparisons were conducted for both overall city noise levels and noise registered on five types of roads with different functionality using the Categorisation Method. The results showed that four of the five cities' characteristics presented a significant correlation with the noise levels (all except for density). The calculated correlations were better for noise levels in the different categories than the overall noise values, with higher explained variability on the streets with more traffic. Therefore, the road categorisation method can be used not only to assess the noise

1 variations within cities, but also to better explain the effect of noise on the analysed city
2 characteristics. The results of the calculated relationships enable the estimation of noise
3 levels both currently and in future urban developments of noise values on different types
4 of streets.
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10 **Keywords:** environmental pollution; urban planning; road traffic noise; road
11 categorisation method; healthenvironmental management
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16 **1. INTRODUCTION**

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20 The mobility of people and goods using individual and collective transport methods has
21 become a real need in contemporary society (Mattioli, 2016). Road, rail, airport, and port
22 infrastructures have been developed to respond to the demand (Mattioli et al., 2020). The
23 United Nations projects that the world's population living in urban areas will increase by
24 a quarter in about 30 years (United Nations, 2019) and such an influx of citizens will put
25 more strain on transport infrastructure. The planning and design of these infrastructures
26 are essential not only to facilitate the movement of flows of passengers and products, but
27 also to reduce or minimise their adverse impact. Many investigations revealed the
28 relationship of the different transport methods with climate change (Hensher, 2008;
29 Wadud, 2011) and air pollution (Dedoussi et al., 2020; Jiménez et al., 2009; WHO, 2006).
30 It is important to note that these transport infrastructures are mainly responsible for
31 environmental noise (Dai et al., 2020; Džambas et al., 2018; Flores et al., 2019; Lee et
32 al., 2014), a pollutant that results in negative effects on human health both physically and
33 psychologically (Foraster et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2019; Nazneen et al., 2020; Thiesse et
34 al., 2018). Some studies revealed the relationship between air pollution and
35 environmental noise in the case of road traffic (López-Aparicio, et al., 2020; Pérez-Prada
36 & Monzón, 2017; Tezel et al., 2019). Therefore, noise research would also benefit the
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development of actions to reduce air pollution and a better understanding of the negative effect of road traffic noise on the health of citizens.

Due to cities' population concentrations, managing environmental noise in these spaces is a major challenge for public authorities given its impact on other closely related areas of society. Some investigations indicated that exposure of populations to environmental noise generated by transport increases the demand for health services, leading to higher associated health costs (Carmona et al., 2017; Linares et al., 2017; Monrad et al., 2019). Another important factor to consider is the effect that traffic noise pollution has on the local economy, especially the price of houses in affected areas (Swoboda et al., 2015; Zheng et al., 2020). This effect on the economy can lead to poor neighbourhoods being exposed to more traffic noise and air pollution with consequent health problems (Casey et al., 2017). These transport infrastructures also play a negative role in the conservation of wildlife in their surroundings (Alquezar & Marcelo, 2019; Guo et al., 2016).

In this regard, the European Noise Directive (END, 2002) provided guidelines for assessing and managing environmental noise in the European Union, introducing strategic noise maps as a basic tool (Montes González et al., 2020a; Paschalidou et al., 2019; Thacher et al., 2020). As a result, the design of action plans to mitigate noise pollution improved (D'Alessandro & Schiavoni et al., 2015; Ögren et al., 2018; Murphy & King, 2010). Estimations indicated that more than 125 million people could actually be exposed to road traffic noise above 55 dB L_{den} . In Europe, road traffic is considered the main source of environmental noise (EEA, 2014). In this framework, World Health Organization recently recommended not exceeding 53 dB for L_{den} noise indicators to minimise negative effects on sleep and health (WHO, 2018).

1 Urban planning of cities can help improve their acoustic quality ([Munir et al., 2021](#)).

2 Some studies focused on predicting traffic noise levels using different urban variables
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4 (Oiamo et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2016). Some factors related to urban and transport
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6 planning in cities (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2010; Khomenko et al., 2020) and
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8 architectural design of building façades (Naish et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2015) may not
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10 only be important for prediction using calculations, but also in the process of on-site
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12 measurements of environmental noise levels (Memoli et al., 2008; Montes González et
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14 al., 2018). The promotion of quiet areas and urban parks can also positively contribute to
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16 the well-being and health of city residents exposed to high traffic noise levels (Kogan et
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18 al., 2018; Rey Gozalo et al., 2019).

25 Studying the spatial and temporal structure of urban noise and its relationship to urban
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27 and architectural variables is important to assess and manage traffic noise in cities. A
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29 good understanding of these factors can improve the prediction, analysis, and prevention
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31 of this polluting agent using effective urban environment planning (Barrigón Morillas et
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33 al., 2018). Among the techniques for spatial sampling of environmental noise levels, the
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35 [Categorisation Method](#) (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2002; Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005)
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37 was proposed as an alternative to the traditional grid method initially established in the
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39 ISO 1996-2:1987 standard (ISO 1996-2:1987). The categorisation method uses sampling
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41 via *in situ* measurements using a previous stratification of the streets in different
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43 categories according to their functionality in connecting different areas of cities.
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45 Strategies based on this street stratification concept obtained good results on the spatial
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47 and temporal distribution of road traffic noise in cities with diverse sizes (Barrigón
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49 Morillas et al., 2015; Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a; Romeu et al., 2011).

58 The objective of [this study is to analyse the capacity of variables related to the size of
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60 cities to explain noise levels on their streets. Categorisation Method has been used to](#)

1 ~~stratify the city streets~~the work is to study the influence that the size of cities and the
2 ~~functional structure of their streets can have on urban noise. The sampling methodology~~
3
4 ~~followed the Categorisation Method. This spatial sampling approach is based on the urban~~
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6 ~~structure and achieves a significant stratification of noise levels as shown in previous~~
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8 ~~studies~~ (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005; Rey Gozalo et al., 2012, 2013a; Romeu et al.,
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10 2011). As this method classifies streets according to their functionality, this study allows
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12 to analyse the relationships between urban noise and variables related to the size of the
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14 city taking into account the mobility of people. Two widely used variables have been used
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16 (population and area) and a new variable less used for this purpose has been added (streets
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18 length). Different sound level measurement campaigns were carried out using this method
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20 in 27 cities from Spain, Portugal and Chile with populations in the range of 2000 to
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22 700,000 inhabitants. The results of this study could help in urban management and in the
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24 evaluation of the effect that the growth models of the cities can have on the urban noise.
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31 32 33 **2. METHODOLOGY**

34 35 36 **2.1 Variables related to the city's size**

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39 Three variables related to the city's size were considered: population, surface area, and
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41 street lengths. Different circumstances, such as the mobility of city residents or the arrival
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43 of visitors due to services offered, probably make the noise level in a city's streets
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45 dependent on variables associated with its size. Obviously, the population, area and street
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47 lengths are related to each other ($r_{Pearson} > 0.95$). However, if a group of cities is
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49 considered, the relationships between these three variables will depend on the specific
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51 city being studied. The city's urban design means that, for different cities with similar
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53 values of any of the studied variables, the values are quite different from the other two.
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1 An essential characteristic of the categorisation method is that it stratifies urban noise
2 according to the functionality of urban roads. Therefore, in addition to assessing the
3 dependence of the city's average noise on variables associated with its size, it allows the
4 analysis of the extent to which the stratified structure of urban noise is related to these
5 variables. Therefore, using the Categorisation Method to study urban noise makes it
6 possible to assess the importance that a city's size variables have on the existing sound
7 levels in its streets considering the streets' functionality. Five street categories were
8 defined in the categorisation method to this end (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005):
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- 10 • Category 1: Preferential streets for connection with other cities and interconnection
11 of those preferential streets.
- 12 • Category 2: Streets that provide access to major distribution nodes in a city or are
13 used as an alternative to Category 1 during traffic saturation.
- 14 • Category 3: Streets that lead to regional roads, streets that provide access from street
15 Categories 1 and 2 to centres of interest in a city (hospitals, shopping malls, etc.), and
16 streets that clearly allow communication between street Categories 1 and 2.
- 17 • Category 4: All of the other streets that clearly allow connections between the three
18 previously defined categories and the principal streets in a city's different districts
19 that were not included in the previously defined categories.
- 20 • Category 5: The rest of a city's streets except for traffic-restricted streets.

21 Table 1 shows each city's characteristics regarding its population, area, population
22 density, and total length of streets. In this study, in addition to using the population density
23 that is usually used as a reference, the population density and length of the city's streets
24 were considered due to the variable street lengths used in the Categorisation Method.
25 This new variable defining the population density is called the linear population density.

26 Population density per unit length was more highly correlated with respect to area,

population and street length ($r_{Pearson} = 0.82 - 0.92$) than population density per unit area ($r_{Pearson} = 0.32 - 0.55$).

Table 1. Cities studied with data on the population, area, surface population density, and total street lengths

City	Population (inhabitants)	Area (km ²)	Population density (inhabitants/km ²)	Street length (m)
Sevilla	699,759	59.27	11,806	527,800
Málaga	566,447	53.44	10,600	479,150
Valladolid	318,461	37.02	8,602	253,082
Vitoria	221,270	30	7,376	250,540
Santander	181,589	15.6	11,640	245,155
Salamanca	155,740	18.05	8,628	181,644
Badajoz	146,832	17.2	8,537	193,027
Valdivia (Chile)	129,952	33	3,938	299,927
Cáceres	92,187	12.66	7,282	161,356
Talavera de la Reina	88,986	12.57	7,079	107,163
Mérida	55,568	10.87	5,112	68,158
Plasencia	40,105	9.63	4,165	87,854
Don Benito	34,540	6.97	4,956	58,919
Almendralejo	33,177	6.03	5,502	48,095
Villanueva de la Serena	25,576	3.43	7,457	59,168
Navalmoral de la Mata	17,103	1.99	8,594	44,778
Zafra	16,218	2.12	7,650	47,448
Coria	12,868	1.1	11,698	27,027
Olivenza	11,814	2.07	5,707	22,955
Miajadas	10,241	2.97	3,448	30,000
Trujillo	9,766	4.06	2,405	42,077
Azuaga	8,501	1.88	4,522	28,150
Campo Maior (Portugal)	8,387	1.3	6,452	25,859
Guareña	7,365	1.27	5,799	27,846
Castuera	6,652	1.38	4,820	28,345
Arroyo de la Luz	6,477	1.17	5,536	23,170
La Coronada	2,238	0.57	3,926	10,939

2.2. Measurement and analysis methodology

1 To conduct a broad study on the cities and the diversity of their urban characteristics,
2 different environmental noise level measurement campaigns were carried out in 27 cities
3 in Spain, Portugal, and Chile with population sizes between approximately 2,000 and
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5 700,000 inhabitants. Figure 1 (a) shows the different cities selected for this study.
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10 At the beginning of the measurements, each city's streets were classified in the five
11 categories defined above in the Categorisation Method. Therefore, all streets were
12 classified according to their functionality in all the studied cities. Figure 1 (b) shows ~~the~~
13 ~~different cities selected for this study and includes, as an example,~~ the stratification of the
14 streets in Valdivia (Chile). A ~~stratified~~-random selection of measurement points in each
15 of these road categories was then carried out ~~using this classification on the streets of the~~
16 ~~residential areas of the cities~~. According to the previous studies for this size range of
17 cities, approximately 10 points are sufficient to obtain a representative sample of the
18 sound level in each category (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005, Carmona del Río et al., 2011;
19 Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a). These studies have also shown that this~~This~~ number does not
20 depend on the size of the city and the category considered (~~Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005;~~
21 ~~Carmona del Río et al., 2011; Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a~~). About 50 points were thus
22 sampled in each city.
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(b)

Figure 1. (a) Location of the cities studied using Google Maps. (b) Stratification of Valdivia's streets.

Temporal sampling was planned by means of short duration sound level measurements given the large number of cities studied. Previous studies have shown that a set of three 15-minute measurements taken during working hours on different days and at different times of the day are representative of the daily noise levels in the urban environments

1 (Rey Gozalo et al., 2013b, 2014; Romeu et al., 2011). In addition, ~~it has been proved~~
2 ~~through the analysis of~~ noise indicators L_d , L_e , L_n and L_{den} measured during one week
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4 (Rey Gozalo et al., 2013b; 2014) or one year (Rey Gozalo et al., 2015), ~~that sound levels~~
5 ~~measured during working hours or during other hours show~~ had a similar spatial
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Class 1 sound level meters were used for the measurements and the calibration was verified before and after each measurement session using a class 1 sound calibrator. The equivalent sound level (L_{Aeq}) was recorded with the microphones placed 1.5 m over the ground (ISO 1996-2:2007) and 1.5 m from the nearest traffic lane. There were no obstacles between the sound sources and microphones during the measurements (Montes González et al. 2020b).

Each category's sound level i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \text{ or } 5$) was obtained in each city as the average of the values measured in that category's points ($L_{Aeq-cat.i}$). Each city's overall sound level ($L_{Aeq-overall}$) was then calculated as a weighted average according to the category's street lengths. Based on these values, the relationships between the overall and category sound levels were studied with variables related to the city's size (population, area, and total street lengths) and population density (surface and linear population density). This analysis was carried out for all the cities studied without differentiating the country in which they were located. Linear regression analyses were conducted between both types of variables, but the decimal logarithm of the urban variables was first calculated. The assumptions of normality (Shapiro-Wilks test), homoscedasticity (Breusch-Pagan test), and linearity (reset test) were verified in the variables analysed. The determination coefficient (R^2) and its significance through the F statistic were obtained to analyse the

1 degree of the relationship between both variables. The standard error was also calculated
2 to provide information on the variability of the dependent variable that was not explained
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4 by the regression line. The F test was also used to analyse the variance and covariance to
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6 compare the slope, intercept, or goodness of fit of the different regression lines obtained
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8 in the different road categories.
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11 12 13 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION** 14 15

16 17 **3.1 Sound level and variables related to the city's size** 18 19

20 In this section, the relationship between the measured sound level and three variables of
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22 a city's size are studied. In addition to the city's average sound level, each category's
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24 levels defined using the Categorisation Method are considered.
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28 29 **3.1.1 Dependence of the city's sound level on its population** 30

31 The population variable is the most widely used to measure a city's size. One factor that
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33 can affect the number of vehicles in a city is the residential population. Consequently, the
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35 noise level on a city's streets is related to the number of vehicles. Two factors of interest
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37 in this relationship are studied in this section. First, the extent to which the variable
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39 population is capable of effectively explaining the variability of a city's average noise is
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41 studied. Second, the extent to which the sound level of the strata defined by the
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43 Categorisation Method is related to this size variable is assessed. Depending on the
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45 residents of each of the cities studied, the values of the sound levels measured in the
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47 streets of each of the categories and the values of the overall level of the city are shown
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49 in Figure 2. The regression lines obtained are also shown. In general, the slopes obtained
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51 in the analysis by categories appear to be similar but seem to differ from the trend for the
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53 overall city. The slope and intercept coefficients, the coefficient of determination (R^2),
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and the standard error of the regression lines are given shown in Table 2. The relationships between the noise levels and population were highly significant ($p < 0.001$) in all road categories as well as considering the overall city.

Figure 2. Scatter diagrams and sound level regression lines in relation to the population.

Table 2. Linear regression parameters between the sound level and population

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log_{10} (population)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	3.847	54.207	0.751	< 0.001	1.512
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	3.844	52.002	0.795	< 0.001	1.341
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	4.104	48.617	0.801	< 0.001	1.397
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	4.756	42.171	0.873	< 0.001	1.240
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	3.645	40.408	0.588	< 0.001	2.082
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	2.901	48.109	0.498	< 0.001	1.990

First, the results for the city's overall sound level ($L_{Aeq-overall}$) shown in Table 2 demonstrates that the population variable can explain almost 50% of the variation in the city's average sound level. This means that there is another 50% whose cause is different from the population variations. Studying the dependence of the sound level of a city's streets considering the urban structure makes it possible to analyse to what extent the

variable population is capable of explaining each category's sound level defined using the Categorisation Method. The results explain the sound level's variability in the categories in a range between 59% (Category 5) and 87% (Category 4). In other words, the variability obtained for the city's overall average sound level improves in all the categories. The variability found in the different categories shows that the highest value is obtained for Category 4, decreasing as categories of greater use are considered, up to Category 1, and finally the lowest value is found in Category 5. To ascertain if these results represent a statistically distinguishable trend, the *F* test was used to compare the variances between the different categories. The results indicate that Category 5's variance significantly differs from that of Categories 2, 3, and 4, although not Category 1. The remaining categories, which have variability explanations between 75% (Category 1) and 87% (Category 4), do not present significant differences in their variance (Table 3).

Table 3. *P* values using the *F* test to compare the slopes of the regression lines related to the city's population to the average sound level of the road category

Categories	1	2	3	4
2	0.567	-	-	-
3	0.698	0.846	-	-
4	0.328	0.700	0.554	-
5	0.116	0.037	0.041	0.012

The results' meaning and relevance demonstrate that strata structure allows a better understanding of the dependence that exists between a city's noise and its residential population than the global average level. However, this is not the most important conclusion that can be drawn. Table 2 demonstrates that the strata structure proposed in the Categorisation Method allows, with high explanations of variability, the prediction of the dependence between a city's residential population and the noise level by strata or groups of streets. Prior studies showed that these strata, in general, have significant

1 differences in their mean values (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005; Carmona del Río et al.,
2 2011; Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a). This opens up interesting possibilities regarding the
3 prediction of urban noise specifically in a city street. Therefore, it is necessary to compare
4 the regression lines obtained for each of the categories.
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10 If the slopes are first analysed, all values are relatively close as shown in Table 2.

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12 ~~Therefore, the results shown in Table 2 can be analysed with respect to the linear~~
13 ~~relationship obtained. If they are considered in the slopes, all the values are relatively~~
14 ~~close. Therefore, e~~
15 Each time the population increases by an order of magnitude,

16 depending on the type of street, the level increases by 3.6 dBA for Category 5,
17 approximately 4.0 dBA for Categories 1, 2, and 3, and 4.8 dBA for Category 4. However,
18 in an analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) using the F test, the slopes of the different
19 categories' regression lines did not significantly differ (p value = 0.461). Therefore, the
20 results indicate that the dependence of a city's residential population on the noise in its
21 streets is statistically similar for all of its streets. This result was found using the

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23 Categorisation Method to study urban noise. However, if the ordinate at the origin of
24 the different categories is analysed, it is higher as greater use categories are considered,
25 from 40 dBA for Category 5 to 52 dBA for Category 1. This gives a base value of the
26 sound level for human agglomerations that oscillates between these two values depending
27 on the type of street considered. Furthermore, in this case, the different categories'
28 ordinates significantly differ according to the F test (p value < 0.001). Therefore, although
29 the increase in urban noise in a city's streets with the residential population is statistically
30 similar in the different types of categories, the same does not occur with the ordinate at
31 the origin. ~~Therefore,~~Consequently, the lines obtained for the categories significantly

32 differ. This result strengthens the strata structure based on the Categorisation Method
33 and indicates that, although in a given city two contiguous categories do not present
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1 significant differences in their mean values, globally, the categories correspond to
2 different sound levels. This conclusion gives the present results the greatest importance,
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4 since it implies that, at least in the range of cities studied with a 300 factor in population,
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6 the population variable linked to the Categorisation Method makes it possible to
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8 predict the sound level in groups of streets in a city with relatively low uncertainties,
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10 which vary between 1.2 dBA and 2.1 dBA.
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15 However, a city's population is not the only determinant of its streets' sound levels. For
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17 similar populations, another cause of variations would be, for example, vehicle use, or
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19 the amount of population concentrated on the streets. Both are associated with the city's
20
21 surface area. For the same number of inhabitants, if the surface area increases, the number
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23 of vehicles will also increase, but if the surface area decreases, the number of vehicles per
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25 unit of surface area can increase. This variable is analysed in the following section.
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31 **3.1.2 Dependence of the city's sound level on its area**

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35 The variable area is also commonly used to measure the size of cities. This is another
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37 factor that affects the need for vehicle use in a city. Larger surfaces usually imply greater
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39 needs for vehicle use and, consequently, may cause higher noise levels in the city. For
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41 this reason, the variable surface area and its relationship with the noise level of a city's
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43 streets were studied. Similar to the previous section, both the relationship with the city's
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45 average level and the urban structure using the Categorisation Method's strata were
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47 considered. A representation of the sound levels measured in the cities studied against
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49 this variable and the linear regression lines is shown in Figure 3. Table 4 presents different
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51 parameters obtained in the linear regression analysis.
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Figure 3. Scatter diagrams and regression lines of the sound level in relation to the surface.

Table 4. Linear regression parameters between the sound level and area

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log ₁₀ (area)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	4.479	68.341	0.782	< 0.001	1.416
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	4.631	65.927	0.838	< 0.001	1.193
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	4.759	63.701	0.830	< 0.001	1.291
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	5.386	59.758	0.860	< 0.001	1.303
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	4.062	54.938	0.561	< 0.001	2.151
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	3.291	58.831	0.492	< 0.001	2.001

According to the results givenshown in Table 4, the significance of all the regression lines is less than 0.001. First, if the city's overall sound level is considered, the variable area explains 49% of the variations in a city's average sound level. This result is similar to that found in the previous section for the population variable. Next, the dependence of the sound level on a city's streets was studied considering the urban structure. The results shown in Table 4 indicate how, in the first four categories, positive linear relations are

obtained between the urban noise and surface area, with explanations for the variability exceeding 78% and even reaching 86%. In addition, there is an increase in the explanation of variability, with respect to 49% of the overall city, in the streets in Category 5, reaching 56%. The results are similar to those found with the population variable. Therefore, the strata structure not only allows a better understanding of the dependence that exists between a city's noise and its surface, but also enables us to describe in detail this dependence according to groups of streets. If a multiple comparison of the variance between the different categories is made using the *F* test, only Category 5 presents significant differences with respect to the rest of the categories as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. *P* values using the *F* test to compare the slopes of the regression lines that are related to the area of the city and the average sound level of the road category

Categories	1	2	3	4
2	0.413	-	-	-
3	0.647	0.709	-	-
4	0.683	0.673	0.961	-
5	0.041	0.006	0.013	0.015

The meaning and relevance of the results with respect to the area variable are considered. First, for this variable, the structure of strata allows a better understanding of the dependence that exists between this structure and a city's noise than the global average level. In addition, the explanations of the variability of the sound level found from the strata structure proposed by the Categorisation Method are similar to those previously found using the population variable. Therefore, they enable the prediction of the dependence between a city's area and the sound level by strata or groups of streets. For this reason, the regression lines in each of the categories are compared.

If the results shown in Table 4 are analysed with respect to the linear relationships and more specifically the slopes of the adjustments, all the values are relatively close. Each

1 time the urban area increases by an order of magnitude, the level increases by 4.1 dBA
2 for Category 5 and approximately 4.5 dBA for Categories 1, 2, and 3, with very similar
3 values. Category 4 experienced the greatest growth in the variable area, with a value of
4 5.4 dBA for an order of magnitude increase in the surface area. However, in reality, if the
5 slopes of the regression lines are compared via an ANCOVA using the F test, a p value
6 > 0.05 is obtained. There are no significant differences between the different slopes of the
7 regression lines obtained in each category. This implies that the increase in the noise level
8 with a city's surface is statistically similar in the different groups of streets. These slope
9 values, when compared with the population variable's values, seem to indicate the
10 importance of urban growth models on the noise level of a city. However, if the values
11 obtained for the ordinate at the origin are analysed according to the categories, their value
12 increases as greater use categories are considered. Its value increases from 55 dBA for
13 Category 5 to 68 dBA for Category 1, which gives a base sound level value for human
14 agglomerations with a reference surface of 1 km² that oscillates between these two values
15 depending on the type of street considered. If the intercepts are analysed using the F test,
16 for any pair of categories compared (p value < 0.001), the intercepts of all of the
17 categories significantly differ. Therefore, similar to the results found with the variable
18 population, with the variable area, the lines found for the categories are also statistically
19 different. As with the variable population, the variable area allows, at least in the range
20 of cities studied with a factor of 100 on the area, the prediction of the noise level in
21 specific streets of a city, with uncertainties that are approximately 1.2 to 2.2 dBA of
22 typical errors.

3.1.3 Dependence of the city's sound level on the total length of its streets

23 In the previous sections, it was proven that the population or area of a city are determining
24 size variables to explain the variability of the sound level in the streets of a city. However,

1 if the urban structure of streets varies or there is a different length of urban roads for
 2 similar population sizes and areas, the sound level in the streets may vary between cities.
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 4 For example, shorter lengths could mean more vehicle density on the streets and
 5 consequently higher noise levels or vice versa. In addition, it is clear that the total length
 6 of the streets in a city, although not commonly used, is an indicator of its size and, in this
 7 sense, it can be expected that significant relationships will be obtained between a city's
 8 sound level and the length of its streets. Figure 4 shows a representation of the dependence
 9 of the sound level with the length of the streets in the cities studied and the regression
 10 lines. The different parameters obtained in the analysis of the linear regression are
 11 presented in Table 6.

Figure 4. Scatter diagrams and regression lines of the sound level in relation to the total length of the streets.

Table 6. Linear regression parameters between the sound level and street length

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log ₁₀ (street length)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	5.568	44.703	0.748	< 0.001	1.521
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	5.572	42.444	0.783	< 0.001	1.378
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	5.994	38.215	0.812	< 0.001	1.357
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	6.756	31.020	0.839	< 0.001	1.398
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	4.958	33.946	0.518	< 0.001	2.255
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	3.836	42.702	0.414	< 0.001	2.149

Table 6 shows that all the relationships between the independent and dependent variables are highly significant (p value < 0.001). In a city's overall sound level, the variable length can explain 41% of the variations in the city's average sound level. The result is lower than those found in the previous sections for the population and area variables. If the dependence of the sound level of a city's streets on the urban structure is studied, the results shown in Table 6 indicate how, in the first four categories, the increase in noise depends on the increase in the street lengths, explaining between approximately 75% and 84% of the variability. The results, while slightly lower than those obtained with the area variable, are similar to those found for the population variable. In the Category 5 streets, a 52% variability was explained. Therefore, for all the strata, in this case the variable length, which is essential for the Categorisation Method, the strata explain the variability of noise in a city better than if the noise was studied globally. For the variable area, Category 5 presents a significantly different variance than the other categories as shown in Table 7. Consequently, the variable length, in the same way as the population and area variables, allows detailing the dependence between urban noise and the different street categories, finding high explanations for the variability.

Table 7. *P* values using the *F* test to compare the slopes of the regression lines that are related to the total length of the city's streets and the road category's average sound level

Categories	1	2	3	4
2	0.637	-	-	-
3	0.573	0.937	-	-
4	0.675	0.949	0.884	-
5	0.044	0.020	0.014	0.020

The results of the linear relationship shown in Table 6 are analysed. The slope values demonstrate that each time the length of urban roads increases by an order of magnitude, the level increases depending on the type of street. A value of 5.0 dBA was obtained for Category 5 and approximately 5.8 dBA for Categories, 1, 2, and 3, very similar values. Category 4 experiences the greatest growth in length, with a value of 6.8 dBA. Despite this apparent difference between the slopes, an analysis of the covariance using the *F* test indicates that they are statistically indistinguishable (*p* value = 0.448). This result is similar to that found with the other two size variables. Greater slopes are obtained than with the other two variables, population and area, which must be associated with the smaller range of the variable length with respect to the ranges of the other two size variables, a factor of 55. If the ordinate's behaviour at the origin for the different categories is studied, its value is significantly higher as categories of greater use (*p* value < 0.001 according to the *F* test) are considered, although there is a slight inversion between Categories 4 and 5. The values range from 31 dBA for Category 4, to 34 dBA for Category 5, and 45 dBA for Category 1. This gives a base value for the sound level for human agglomerations that varies between these two values depending on the type of street that is considered. All the values are very low, which is related to a greater number of orders of magnitude until reaching the zero order of the variable represented. In fact, in Categories 4 and 5, it could be considered a base level in the absence of people, given that it corresponds to the reference of 1 m in length of the city's streets.

1 The stratification of urban roads according to their functionality is a useful tool for urban
2 planners to estimate noise values using variables such as population, area and street
3 length. Cities will continue to grow in the coming years and it is important to estimate the
4 possible effects on the sound environment. Area and population are the variables that
5 explain the greatest variability in sound levels on main streets (Categories 1 to 3) and
6 residential streets (Category 4 and 5), respectively. Considering that Categories 1 to 3
7 correspond to the streets more commonly used by citizens, this result may indicate that
8 the area occupied by the city is an influential factor in the need for vehicle use from
9 residential areas. This is not the case for categories 4 and 5, which are more influenced
10 by the increase in population in residential areas as the city grows. However, these
11 differences in the explanation of variability are not significant between the population,
12 surface area and street length variables. Therefore, any of these variables can be used as
13 predictors of noise levels with relatively low uncertainties.
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3.2 Sound level and variables related to population densities

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36 Population density is traditionally associated with the population in a given environment
37 relative to that environment's area. In this work, for reasons that will be explained, this
38 variable is called surface density (SD). However, as already indicated, this study is based
39 on the Categorisation Method, which helps explore new possibilities to ascertain the
40 relationship between sound level and population density. In particular, a city's population
41 with respect to the length of its streets was also studied. This variable is called linear
42 density (LD). Therefore, in this section, two types of population density were considered:
43 density per unit area (SD) and density per unit length (LD).
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56 As shown in Section 3.1, the population, area, and length variables from which these two
57 new variables (SD and LD) are obtained lead to a positive linear relationship for the sound
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1 level in the streets. The three size variables are closely related to each other. Therefore, it
2 is mathematically difficult to predict what dependency there will be between the sound
3 level and new density variables. In fact, it is not even possible to foresee that any
4 significant dependence will exist.
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10 **3.2.1 Dependence of the city's sound level on the surface population density**

11 The SD variable is complex when it comes to foreseeing what relationship it has with the
12 sound level a city's streets. For similar population values, the higher the city's surface
13 density, the smaller the surface area and, consequently, the less need for vehicle use. Also,
14 more people per unit of surface area may imply a higher noise level. The same type of
15 analysis could be applied considering the surface area constant. Therefore, this is an
16 interesting variable to study. Figure 5 shows the representation of the sound level against
17 the variable density and regression lines obtained. Table 8 presents different parameters
18 obtained in the linear regression analysis.
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Figure 5. Scatter diagrams and sound level regression lines with respect to the surface population density.

Table 8. Linear regression parameters between sound level and population density

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log ₁₀ (population density)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	6.052	48.773	0.126	> 0.05	2.835
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	7.343	41.894	0.190*	< 0.05	2.663
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	6.562	42.415	0.138	> 0.05	2.908
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	9.197	28.933	0.220*	< 0.05	3.070
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	7.804	28.393	0.182*	< 0.05	2.936
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	5.538	40.306	0.123	> 0.05	2.630

According to the results shown in Table 8, not all the relationships studied are significant and none are highly significant. The significant relationships (p value < 0.05) are found for the dependence of the sound level with the surface density in Categories 2, 4, and 5. Both the sound levels in Categories 1 and 3 as well as the overall sound level in the city do not have a significant relationship with the population's surface density. Therefore, the variable SD is clearly much less suitable for studying urban noise than the variables

1 directly related to the city's size. In fact, if the variances obtained for the same road
 2 category between the different urban variables (population, surface area, and length) are
 3 compared using the F test, the results show that, except for Category 5, there are
 4 significant differences between the lines obtained with any of the three size variables and
 5 those obtained with the variable SD (Table 9).
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11 Table 9. P values obtained from the comparison in the same category of the variance of
 12 the regression lines obtained for the population, area, length, and linear density (LD)
 13 variables with respect to the variances of the variable SD using the F test
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Category	Population	Area	Length	LD
1	0.003	< 0.001	0.003	0.005
2	0.002	< 0.001	0.002	0.005
3	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.005
4	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.008
5	0.092	0.127	0.194	0.090

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 30 Surface density significantly explains the variability of sound levels recorded in
 31 Categories 2, 4, and 5 at a percentage between 18% and 22%. This percentage is low and
 32 if the variance of these categories is compared with those that do not show significant
 33 relationships, the results of the F test demonstrate that there are no significant differences
 34 between their variances (p value > 0.05). However, despite the low variability explained
 35 by the surface density, the category structure explains the variability of a city's noise with
 36 its surface density.
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49 3.2.2 Dependence of the city's sound level on its linear population density

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 52 The previous sections demonstrated that the city's population or street lengths determine
 53 the size variables to explain the variability of the sound level in the city's streets. A new
 54 variable of density will be explored in this section. This new variable, as previously
 55 defined, is obtained as the quotient of the city's population between the length of its
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streets, which is called the linear population density (LD). To the best of our knowledge, this variable is seldom used to study urban noise. In this study, LD is a variable that arises naturally given the use of the variable length in the Categorisation Method. Similar to the traditional population density variable (SD), this variable is defined from two variables that present a statistically significant increase in the sound level as the variable increases. However, for similar population sizes, the urban structure of streets can vary or there can be differences in the length of the streets, which can lead to unclear trends in the sound level. However, in turn, the sound level's dependence on this variable can be closely related to urban planning. In principle, the difficulty of predicting the existence of relationships between sound levels and the LD variable is similar to that for the SD variable. The results achieved with this new variable are then analysed. Figure 6 represents the dependence of the sound level with the variable LD and the regression lines. The different parameters obtained in the linear regression analysis are presented in Table 10.

Figure 6. Scatter diagrams and sound level regression lines with respect to the linear population density.

Table 10. Linear regression parameters between the sound level and linear population density (LD)

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log ₁₀ (linear population density)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	9.653	74.628	0.588	< 0.001	1.946
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	9.656	72.485	0.639	< 0.001	1.779
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	10.090	70.339	0.602	< 0.001	1.977
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	12.404	67.555	0.738	< 0.001	1.780
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	10.360	61.115	0.591	< 0.001	2.076
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	8.662	63.916	0.552	< 0.001	1.879

This variable's result is very interesting, even more so if it is compared with that obtained in the previous section for surface density and if it is taken into account that the two variables from which it is defined have high explanations for the sound level's variability. Table 10 shows that all the relationships are highly significant (p value < 0.001). Moreover, the explanations of the variability although in general somewhat lower than the values obtained for the population or length variables have a value that in all cases exceeds 50%. Therefore, correlation coefficients (R^2) above 0.74 are obtained for all the regression lines. Of note, in addition, as was the case with the population, area, and length variables, the LD variable has a significantly different variance than the SD variable in Categories 1 to 4 (Table 6). First, if the city's overall sound level is considered, the variable LD explains 55% of the variations in a city's average sound level. For the city as a whole, this result is the highest of the variables studied. Therefore, the variable LD seems to be the best variable to use to study a city's average noise. Next, the extent to which this variable is capable of explaining the sound level of each stratum of roads defined by the categorisation method is analysed. Table 10 indicates how the five categories explain the increase in noise by the increase in linear density, with explanations

1 of the variability from 59% (Categories 1 and 5) to 74% in Category 4. Therefore, a
2 variable is obtained that explains the variability of noise in a city for all strata that is better
3 than if the noise is studied globally. Furthermore, the structure of the strata allows, with
4 high explanations of the variability, foreseeing the dependence between a density variable
5 and the sound level by strata or groups of streets. However, if an inferential analysis is
6 conducted using the F test, no statistically significant differences are found in the
7 variances of these regression lines. In addition, as with the size variables, the variable LD
8 has significantly different explanations of the variability than those obtained using the
9 variable SD in all of the categories, except Category 5 (Table 6).
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22 Next, the results shown in Table 10 regarding the linear relationship are analysed. All the
23 slope values are relatively close. Each time a city's linear density increases by an order
24 of magnitude, the sound level increases depending on the type of street by almost 10 dBA
25 for Categories 1, 2, 3, and 5 and 12 dBA for Category 4. However, analysing the
26 covariance using the F test demonstrates that these slopes do not present significant
27 differences (p value = 0.727) and the increase in the sound level by street categories is
28 the same when the variable LD is used. These values of the slopes naturally linked to the
29 variable's small range may indicate that a city's population per unit length of urban roads
30 is an important variable for controlling the city's existing sound level. Analysing the
31 original order shows that its value increases as greater use categories are considered. The
32 values range from 61 dBA for Category 5 to 75 dBA for Category 1. These values also
33 have significant differences according to the F test ($p < 0.001$). These results, which give
34 a base value of the sound level according to the type of street considered, naturally have
35 such high values due to the relationship between the zero value of the LD variable and
36 the structures of the cities. Bear in mind that the zero value corresponds to a linear density
37 of 1 inhabitant for each meter of street. Consequently, most cities have negative variable
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1 LD values. Furthermore, the results show that for this variable, the categories correspond
2 to different sound levels. The new density variable allows the estimation of the sound
3 level by groups of streets with uncertainties in general somewhat greater than those
4 obtained with the size variables. Nevertheless, these are relatively low and very uniform
5 in all of the strata a range of 1.8 to 2.1 dBA with respect to the standard error.
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12 The area, population and street length variables were positively correlated with noise
13 levels. However, there may be differences in the urban planning of the cities studied,
14 despite the relationships between these three variables. In this way, new variables may
15 result from the combination of these variables that may contribute to regulate the increase
16 in noise levels due to future growth of cities. Population density predicted low
17 percentages of sound variability as shown above. This may indicate that urban growth
18 based on higher population densities in cities does not necessarily imply less use of
19 vehicles. However, linear density proved to be a good predictor. Increasing the length of
20 streets for the same population can lead to a decrease in noise levels. Increasing
21 alternative roads or long ring roads does not seem to lead to a substantial increase in car
22 use, but may lead to lower traffic density and improvements in vehicle distribution. In
23 summary, the results show that it is not proven that less dense cities will decrease their
24 noise levels. However, increasing the number of roads for equal population decreases the
25 use per unit length of road.
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48 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

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52 The relationships between urban variables related to the size of a city and noise levels for
53 categories of streets according to their use have been analysed.~~This paper presented an~~
54 ~~analysis of the variability of traffic noise pollution levels by comparing environmental~~
55 ~~noise levels measured in 27 cities in Spain, Portugal, and Chile with respect to five of~~
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~~their urban characteristics. Three of these variables were associated with the size of the cities considered in this study: the population, surface area, and length of the streets. Two population density variables, usually called the population density, were also obtained from the quotient between the population and surface area, and a new variable called the linear density was obtained from the quotient between the population and length of the streets.~~

~~The five categories proposed by the categorisation method allowed the study of these relationship considering not only the cities' average noise, but also the average noise by groups of streets.~~

The results found indicated that, ~~in~~ the variables associated to the size of the cities (population, area, street length): explain a higher variability of urban noise when it is analysed by strata. A classification of urban roads according to their functionality is useful in urban planning to significantly stratify urban noise and to establish estimates from urban variables. For the range of cities studied (population from 2,238 to 699,759 inhabitant), the population, surface area, and length variables allowed the prediction of the noise level in streets categories with uncertainties of approximately 1.2 to 2.3 dBA. These linear regression models can also help predict noise levels on different road categories for future variations in city size. The noise level increased between 3.6 and 6.8 dBA by an order of magnitude depending on the variable and street category. Regarding the road categories, these urban variables explain a greater variability (> 75%) in streets with the highest noise levels (Categories 1 to 4). These urban roads are of greatest interest to city managers because of their greater negative impact on health.

- ~~For all the size variables, the explanations for the variability of urban noise analysed by strata were superior to those obtained for average city noise.~~

- ~~For Categories 1 to 4, the explanations for the variability did not present significant differences and in all of the cases, they were higher than 75%, in some cases reaching values that explained the variability of urban noise in groups of streets higher than 85%.~~
- ~~In general, only the explanations of variability obtained for Category 5 were significantly different from those obtained for the rest of the variables.~~
- ~~The explanations of variability obtained in Category 5 ranged from 52% for the length variable to 59% for the population variable.~~
- ~~The population and surface area variables explained approximately 50% of the average noise variability in cities. The length variable was 41%.~~
- ~~In the population, surface area, and length variables, the range of cities studied were factors of 300, 100, and 55, respectively, and the linear relationship obtained by strata allowed the prediction of the noise level in specific groups of streets in a city, with uncertainties of approximately 1.2 to 2.3 dBA depending on the variable.~~
- ~~The sound level regression lines related to the three city size variables allowed the estimation that each time these variables increased by an order of magnitude, the noise level increased between 3.6 and 6.8 dBA depending on the variable and street category.~~

In the variables related to population density, the findings demonstrated that: the surface density variable had a low explanation for the variability of sound levels recorded in road categories. However, the linear density variable obtained statistically significant relationships in all of the categories with relatively low and very uniform uncertainties (standard error between 1.8 and 2.1 dBA). In addition, linear density was the best predictor of the overall average level of the city. An increase in the population of a city leads to an increase in noise levels. However, this growth can be compensated by

appropriate development of urban roads. In this way, the population will not collapse urban roads and will be able to take alternative roads to reach their destination.

- ~~• The surface density variable resulting from two variables that provided explanations for the sound level's variability did not lead to significant relationships to explain the variability of the city's average noise. Instead, statistically significant relationships were obtained in Categories 2, 4, and 5. The explanations for the variability in these cases were low, between 18% and 22%.~~
- ~~• However, the linear density variable (also obtained from two variables with high explanations of the sound level's variability) obtained statistically significant relationships in all of the strata, with similar or even better values of the variability in Category 5 or the city's overall average level.~~
- ~~• The linear density variable with a range in a factor 6.5 caused relationships that allowed the estimation of the sound level by groups of streets with relatively low and very uniform uncertainties in all of strata, with a standard error between 1.8 and 2.1 dBA.~~

Finally, future lines of research are emerging from the results of this study. Increasing the number of cities could allow to study differences between city types, countries, etc. New variables that consider street lengths according to the Categorisation Method typologies may also allow improvements in the dependence on noise levels and help to better understand the relationships between the urban planning of cities and the noise levels of their streets.

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Variability of Traffic Noise Pollution Levels as a Function of City Size Variables

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ABSTRACT

Noise levels measured in 27 cities with different areas (from 0.6 km² to 59.27 km²) and populations (from approximately 2,000 to 70,000 inhabitants) were compared with respect to five different urban characteristics (population, area, total street length, density, and linear density). Comparisons were conducted for both overall city noise levels and noise registered on five types of roads with different functionality using the Categorisation Method. The results showed that four of the five cities' characteristics presented a significant correlation with the noise levels (all except for density). The calculated correlations were better for noise levels in the different categories than the overall noise values, with higher explained variability on the streets with more traffic. Therefore, the road categorisation method can be used not only to assess the noise variations within cities, but also to better explain the effect of noise on the analysed city

1 characteristics. The results of the calculated relationships enable the estimation of noise
2 levels both currently and in future urban developments of noise values on different types
3 of streets.
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8 **Keywords:** environmental pollution; urban planning; road traffic noise; road
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11 categorisation method; environmental management
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13 14 **1. INTRODUCTION** 15

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18 The mobility of people and goods using individual and collective transport methods has
19 become a real need in contemporary society (Mattioli, 2016). Road, rail, airport, and port
20 infrastructures have been developed to respond to the demand (Mattioli et al., 2020). The
21 United Nations projects that the world's population living in urban areas will increase by
22 a quarter in about 30 years (United Nations, 2019) and such an influx of citizens will put
23 more strain on transport infrastructure. The planning and design of these infrastructures
24 are essential not only to facilitate the movement of flows of passengers and products, but
25 also to reduce or minimise their adverse impact. Many investigations revealed the
26 relationship of the different transport methods with climate change (Hensher, 2008;
27 Wadud, 2011) and air pollution (Dedoussi et al., 2020; Jiménez et al., 2009; WHO, 2006).
28 It is important to note that these transport infrastructures are mainly responsible for
29 environmental noise (Dai et al., 2020; Džambas et al., 2018; Flores et al., 2019; Lee et
30 al., 2014), a pollutant that results in negative effects on human health both physically and
31 psychologically (Foraster et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2019; Nazneen et al., 2020; Thiesse et
32 al., 2018). Some studies revealed the relationship between air pollution and
33 environmental noise in the case of road traffic (López-Aparicio, et al., 2020; Pérez-Prada
34 & Monzón, 2017; Tezel et al., 2019). Therefore, noise research would also benefit the
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1 development of actions to reduce air pollution and a better understanding of the negative
2 effect of road traffic noise on the health of citizens.
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5 Due to cities' population concentrations, managing environmental noise in these spaces
6 is a major challenge for public authorities given its impact on other closely related areas
7 of society. Some investigations indicated that exposure of populations to environmental
8 noise generated by transport increases the demand for health services, leading to higher
9 associated health costs (Carmona et al., 2017; Linares et al., 2017; Monrad et al., 2019).
10 Another important factor to consider is the effect that traffic noise pollution has on the
11 local economy, especially the price of houses in affected areas (Swoboda et al., 2015;
12 Zheng et al., 2020). This effect on the economy can lead to poor neighbourhoods being
13 exposed to more traffic noise and air pollution with consequent health problems (Casey
14 et al., 2017). These transport infrastructures also play a negative role in the conservation
15 of wildlife in their surroundings (Alquezar & Marcelo, 2019; Guo et al., 2016).
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19 In this regard, the European Noise Directive (END, 2002) provided guidelines for
20 assessing and managing environmental noise in the European Union, introducing
21 strategic noise maps as a basic tool (Montes González et al., 2020a; Paschalidou et al.,
22 2019; Thacher et al., 2020). As a result, the design of action plans to mitigate noise
23 pollution improved (D'Alessandro & Schiavoni et al., 2015; Ögren et al., 2018; Murphy
24 & King, 2010). Estimations indicated that more than 125 million people could actually
25 be exposed to road traffic noise above 55 dB L_{den} . In Europe, road traffic is considered
26 the main source of environmental noise (EEA, 2014). In this framework, World Health
27 Organization recently recommended not exceeding 53 dB for L_{den} noise indicators to
28 minimise negative effects on sleep and health (WHO, 2018).
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1 Urban planning of cities can help improve their acoustic quality (Munir et al., 2021).
2 Some studies focused on predicting traffic noise levels using different urban variables
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4 (Oiamo et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2016). Some factors related to urban and transport
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6 planning in cities (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2010; Khomenko et al., 2020) and
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8 architectural design of building façades (Naish et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2015) may not
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10 only be important for prediction using calculations, but also in the process of on-site
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12 measurements of environmental noise levels (Memoli et al., 2008; Montes González et
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14 al., 2018). The promotion of quiet areas and urban parks can also positively contribute to
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16 the well-being and health of city residents exposed to high traffic noise levels (Kogan et
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18 al., 2018; Rey Gozalo et al., 2019).

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25 Studying the spatial and temporal structure of urban noise and its relationship to urban
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27 and architectural variables is important to assess and manage traffic noise in cities. A
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29 good understanding of these factors can improve the prediction, analysis, and prevention
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31 of this polluting agent using effective urban environment planning (Barrigón Morillas et
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33 al., 2018). Among the techniques for spatial sampling of environmental noise levels, the
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35 Categorisation Method (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2002; Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005)
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37 was proposed as an alternative to the traditional grid method initially established in the
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39 ISO 1996-2:1987 standard (ISO 1996-2:1987). The categorisation method uses sampling
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41 via *in situ* measurements using a previous stratification of the streets in different
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43 categories according to their functionality in connecting different areas of cities.
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45 Strategies based on this street stratification concept obtained good results on the spatial
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47 and temporal distribution of road traffic noise in cities with diverse sizes (Barrigón
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49 Morillas et al., 2015; Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a; Romeu et al., 2011).

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52 The objective of this study is to analyse the capacity of variables related to the size of
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54 cities to explain noise levels on their streets. Categorisation Method has been used to
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1 stratify the city streets (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005; Rey Gozalo et al., 2012, 2013a;
2 Romeu et al., 2011). As this method classifies streets according to their functionality,
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4 this study allows to analyse the relationships between urban noise and variables related
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6 to the size of the city taking into account the mobility of people. Two widely used
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8 variables have been used (population and area) and a new variable less used for this
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10 purpose has been added (streets length). Different sound level measurement campaigns
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12 were carried out using this method in 27 cities from Spain, Portugal and Chile with
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14 populations in the range of 2000 to 700,000 inhabitants. The results of this study could
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16 help in urban management and in the evaluation of the effect that the growth models of
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18 the cities can have on the urban noise.
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25 **2. METHODOLOGY**

26 **2.1 Variables related to the city's size**

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29 Three variables related to the city's size were considered: population, surface area, and
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31 street lengths. Different circumstances, such as the mobility of city residents or the arrival
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33 of visitors due to services offered, probably make the noise level in a city's streets
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35 dependent on variables associated with its size. Obviously, the population, area and street
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37 lengths are related to each other ($r_{Pearson} > 0.95$). However, if a group of cities is
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39 considered, the relationships between these three variables will depend on the specific
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41 city being studied. The city's urban design means that, for different cities with similar
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43 values of any of the studied variables, the values are quite different from the other two.
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52 An essential characteristic of the categorisation method is that it stratifies urban noise
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54 according to the functionality of urban roads. Therefore, in addition to assessing the
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56 dependence of the city's average noise on variables associated with its size, it allows the
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58 analysis of the extent to which the stratified structure of urban noise is related to these
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1 variables. Therefore, using the Categorisation Method to study urban noise makes it
2 possible to assess the importance that a city's size variables have on the existing sound
3 levels in its streets considering the streets' functionality. Five street categories were
4 defined in the categorisation method to this end (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005):
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10 • Category 1: Preferential streets for connection with other cities and interconnection
11 of those preferential streets.
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- 13 • Category 2: Streets that provide access to major distribution nodes in a city or are
14 used as an alternative to Category 1 during traffic saturation.
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- 16 • Category 3: Streets that lead to regional roads, streets that provide access from street
17 Categories 1 and 2 to centres of interest in a city (hospitals, shopping malls, etc.), and
18 streets that clearly allow communication between street Categories 1 and 2.
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- 20 • Category 4: All of the other streets that clearly allow connections between the three
21 previously defined categories and the principal streets in a city's different districts
22 that were not included in the previously defined categories.
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- 24 • Category 5: The rest of a city's streets except for traffic-restricted streets.
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38 Table 1 shows each city's characteristics regarding its population, area, population
39 density, and total length of streets. In this study, in addition to using the population density
40 that is usually used as a reference, the population density and length of the city's streets
41 were considered due to the variable street lengths used in the Categorisation Method. This
42 new variable defining the population density is called the linear population density.
43 Population density per unit length was more highly correlated with respect to area,
44 population and street length ($r_{Pearson} = 0.82 - 0.92$) than population density per unit area
45 ($r_{Pearson} = 0.32 - 0.55$).
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Table 1. Cities studied with data on the population, area, surface population density, and total street lengths

City	Population (inhabitants)	Area (km ²)	Population density (inhabitants/km ²)	Street length (m)
Sevilla	699,759	59.27	11,806	527,800
Málaga	566,447	53.44	10,600	479,150
Valladolid	318,461	37.02	8,602	253,082
Vitoria	221,270	30	7,376	250,540
Santander	181,589	15.6	11,640	245,155
Salamanca	155,740	18.05	8,628	181,644
Badajoz	146,832	17.2	8,537	193,027
Valdivia (Chile)	129,952	33	3,938	299,927
Cáceres	92,187	12.66	7,282	161,356
Talavera de la Reina	88,986	12.57	7,079	107,163
Mérida	55,568	10.87	5,112	68,158
Plasencia	40,105	9.63	4,165	87,854
Don Benito	34,540	6.97	4,956	58,919
Almendralejo	33,177	6.03	5,502	48,095
Villanueva de la Serena	25,576	3.43	7,457	59,168
Navalmoral de la Mata	17,103	1.99	8,594	44,778
Zafra	16,218	2.12	7,650	47,448
Coria	12,868	1.1	11,698	27,027
Olivenza	11,814	2.07	5,707	22,955
Miajadas	10,241	2.97	3,448	30,000
Trujillo	9,766	4.06	2,405	42,077
Azuaga	8,501	1.88	4,522	28,150
Campo Maior (Portugal)	8,387	1.3	6,452	25,859
Guareña	7,365	1.27	5,799	27,846
Castuera	6,652	1.38	4,820	28,345
Arroyo de la Luz	6,477	1.17	5,536	23,170
La Coronada	2,238	0.57	3,926	10,939

2.2. Measurement and analysis methodology

To conduct a broad study on the cities and the diversity of their urban characteristics, different environmental noise level measurement campaigns were carried out in 27 cities

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in Spain, Portugal, and Chile with population sizes between approximately 2,000 and 700,000 inhabitants. Figure 1 (a) shows the different cities selected for this study.

At the beginning of the measurements, each city's streets were classified in the five categories defined above in the Categorisation Method. Therefore, all streets were classified according to their functionality in all the studied cities. Figure 1 (b) shows the stratification of the streets in Valdivia (Chile). A random selection of measurement points in each of these road categories was then carried out. According to the previous studies for this size range of cities, approximately 10 points are sufficient to obtain a representative sample of the sound level in each category (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005, Carmona del Río et al., 2011; Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a). These studies have also shown that this number does not depend on the size of the city and the category considered. About 50 points were thus sampled in each city.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. (a) Location of the cities studied using Google Maps. (b) Stratification of Valdivia's streets.

Temporal sampling was planned by means of short duration sound level measurements given the large number of cities studied. Previous studies have shown that a set of three 15-minute measurements taken during working hours on different days and at different times of the day are representative of the daily noise levels in the urban environments (Rey Gozalo et al., 2013b, 2014; Romeu et al., 2011). In addition, noise indicators L_d , L_e , L_n and L_{den} measured during one week (Rey Gozalo et al., 2013b; 2014) or one year (Rey Gozalo et al., 2015), had a similar spatial variability in the different streets of a city (all those that are not drastically restricted by traffic, so that they can be considered rather pedestrian). That is, essentially, the temporal structure of urban noise is based on road traffic flowing through its streets of a city.

Class 1 sound level meters were used for the measurements and the calibration was verified before and after each measurement session using a class 1 sound calibrator. The

1 equivalent sound level (L_{Aeq}) was recorded with the microphones placed 1.5 m over the
2 ground (ISO 1996-2:2007) and 1.5 m from the nearest traffic lane. There were no
3
4 obstacles between the sound sources and microphones during the measurements (Montes
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6 González et al. 2020b).
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10 Each category's sound level i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4,$ or 5) was obtained in each city as the average
11 of the values measured in that category's points ($L_{Aeq-cat.i}$). Each city's overall sound level
12 ($L_{Aeq-overall}$) was then calculated as a weighted average according to the category's street
13 lengths. Based on these values, the relationships between the overall and category sound
14 levels were studied with variables related to the city's size (population, area, and total
15 street lengths) and population density (surface and linear population density). This
16 analysis was carried out for all the cities studied without differentiating the country in
17 which they were located. Linear regression analyses were conducted between both types
18 of variables, but the decimal logarithm of the urban variables was first calculated. The
19 assumptions of normality (Shapiro-Wilks test), homoscedasticity (Breusch-Pagan test),
20 and linearity (reset test) were verified in the variables analysed. The determination
21 coefficient (R^2) and its significance through the F statistic were obtained to analyse the
22 degree of the relationship between both variables. The standard error was also calculated
23 to provide information on the variability of the dependent variable that was not explained
24 by the regression line. The F test was also used to analyse the variance and covariance to
25 compare the slope, intercept, or goodness of fit of the different regression lines obtained
26 in the different road categories.
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3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Sound level and variables related to the city's size

In this section, the relationship between the measured sound level and three variables of a city's size are studied. In addition to the city's average sound level, each category's levels defined using the Categorisation Method are considered.

3.1.1 Dependence of the city's sound level on its population

The population variable is the most widely used to measure a city's size. One factor that can affect the number of vehicles in a city is the residential population. Consequently, the noise level on a city's streets is related to the number of vehicles. Two factors of interest in this relationship are studied in this section. First, the extent to which the variable population is capable of effectively explaining the variability of a city's average noise is studied. Second, the extent to which the sound level of the strata defined by the Categorisation Method is related to this size variable is assessed. Depending on the residents of each of the cities studied, the values of the sound levels measured in the streets of each of the categories and the values of the overall level of the city are shown in Figure 2. The regression lines obtained are also shown. In general, the slopes obtained in the analysis by categories appear to be similar but seem to differ from the trend for the overall city. The slope and intercept coefficients, the coefficient of determination (R^2), and the standard error of the regression lines are given in Table 2. The relationships between the noise levels and population were highly significant ($p < 0.001$) in all road categories as well as considering the overall city.

Figure 2. Scatter diagrams and sound level regression lines in relation to the population.

Table 2. Linear regression parameters between the sound level and population

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log ₁₀ (population)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	3.847	54.207	0.751	< 0.001	1.512
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	3.844	52.002	0.795	< 0.001	1.341
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	4.104	48.617	0.801	< 0.001	1.397
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	4.756	42.171	0.873	< 0.001	1.240
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	3.645	40.408	0.588	< 0.001	2.082
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	2.901	48.109	0.498	< 0.001	1.990

First, the results for the city's overall sound level ($L_{Aeq-overall}$) shown in Table 2 demonstrates that the population variable can explain almost 50% of the variation in the city's average sound level. This means that there is another 50% whose cause is different from the population variations. Studying the dependence of the sound level of a city's streets considering the urban structure makes it possible to analyse to what extent the variable population is capable of explaining each category's sound level defined using the Categorisation Method. The results explain the sound level's variability in the categories in a range between 59% (Category 5) and 87% (Category 4). In other words,

1 the variability obtained for the city's overall average sound level improves in all the
 2 categories. The variability found in the different categories shows that the highest value
 3 is obtained for Category 4, decreasing as categories of greater use are considered, up to
 4 Category 1, and finally the lowest value is found in Category 5. To ascertain if these
 5 results represent a statistically distinguishable trend, the *F* test was used to compare the
 6 variances between the different categories. The results indicate that Category 5's variance
 7 significantly differs from that of Categories 2, 3, and 4, although not Category 1. The
 8 remaining categories, which have variability explanations between 75% (Category 1) and
 9 87% (Category 4), do not present significant differences in their variance (Table 3).
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23 Table 3. *P* values using the *F* test to compare the slopes of the regression lines related to
 24 the city's population to the average sound level of the road category
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Categories	1	2	3	4
2	0.567	-	-	-
3	0.698	0.846	-	-
4	0.328	0.700	0.554	-
5	0.116	0.037	0.041	0.012

28 The results' meaning and relevance demonstrate that strata structure allows a better
 29 understanding of the dependence that exists between a city's noise and its residential
 30 population than the global average level. However, this is not the most important
 31 conclusion that can be drawn. Table 2 demonstrates that the strata structure proposed in
 32 the Categorisation Method allows, with high explanations of variability, the prediction of
 33 the dependence between a city's residential population and the noise level by strata or
 34 groups of streets. Prior studies showed that these strata, in general, have significant
 35 differences in their mean values (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005; Carmona del Río et al.,
 36 2011; Rey Gozalo et al., 2013a). This opens up interesting possibilities regarding the
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1 prediction of urban noise specifically in a city street. Therefore, it is necessary to compare
2 the regression lines obtained for each of the categories.
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5 If the slopes are first analysed, all values are relatively close as shown in Table 2.
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7 Therefore, each time the population increases by an order of magnitude, depending on
8 the type of street, the level increases by 3.6 dBA for Category 5, approximately 4.0 dBA
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10 for Categories 1, 2, and 3, and 4.8 dBA for Category 4. However, in an analysis of
11 covariance (ANCOVA) using the F test, the slopes of the different categories' regression
12 lines did not significantly differ (p value = 0.461). Therefore, the results indicate that the
13 dependence of a city's residential population on the noise in its streets is statistically
14 similar for all of its streets. This result was found using the Categorisation Method to
15 study urban noise. However, if the ordinate at the origin of the different categories is
16 analysed, it is higher as greater use categories are considered, from 40 dBA for Category
17 5 to 52 dBA for Category 1. This gives a base value of the sound level for human
18 agglomerations that oscillates between these two values depending on the type of street
19 considered. Furthermore, in this case, the different categories' ordinates significantly
20 differ according to the F test (p value < 0.001). Therefore, although the increase in urban
21 noise in a city's streets with the residential population is statistically similar in the
22 different types of categories, the same does not occur with the ordinate at the origin.
23 Consequently, the lines obtained for the categories significantly differ. This result
24 strengthens the strata structure based on the Categorisation Method and indicates that,
25 although in a given city two contiguous categories do not present significant differences
26 in their mean values, globally, the categories correspond to different sound levels. This
27 conclusion gives the present results the greatest importance, since it implies that, at least
28 in the range of cities studied with a 300 factor in population, the population variable
29 linked to the Categorisation Method makes it possible to predict the sound level in groups
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1 of streets in a city with relatively low uncertainties, which vary between 1.2 dBA and 2.1
2 dBA.
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5 However, a city's population is not the only determinant of its streets' sound levels. For
6 similar populations, another cause of variations would be, for example, vehicle use, or
7 the amount of population concentrated on the streets. Both are associated with the city's
8 surface area. For the same number of inhabitants, if the surface area increases, the number
9 of vehicles will also increase, but if the surface area decreases, the number of vehicles per
10 unit of surface area can increase. This variable is analysed in the following section.
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22 **3.1.2 Dependence of the city's sound level on its area**

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25 The variable area is also commonly used to measure the size of cities. This is another
26 factor that affects the need for vehicle use in a city. Larger surfaces usually imply greater
27 needs for vehicle use and, consequently, may cause higher noise levels in the city. For
28 this reason, the variable surface area and its relationship with the noise level of a city's
29 streets were studied. Similar to the previous section, both the relationship with the city's
30 average level and the urban structure using the Categorisation Method's strata were
31 considered. A representation of the sound levels measured in the cities studied against
32 this variable and the linear regression lines is shown in Figure 3. Table 4 presents different
33 parameters obtained in the linear regression analysis.
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Figure 3. Scatter diagrams and regression lines of the sound level in relation to the surface.

Table 4. Linear regression parameters between the sound level and area

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log ₁₀ (area)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	4.479	68.341	0.782	< 0.001	1.416
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	4.631	65.927	0.838	< 0.001	1.193
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	4.759	63.701	0.830	< 0.001	1.291
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	5.386	59.758	0.860	< 0.001	1.303
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	4.062	54.938	0.561	< 0.001	2.151
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	3.291	58.831	0.492	< 0.001	2.001

According to the results given in Table 4, the significance of all the regression lines is less than 0.001. First, if the city's overall sound level is considered, the variable area explains 49% of the variations in a city's average sound level. This result is similar to that found in the previous section for the population variable. Next, the dependence of the sound level on a city's streets was studied considering the urban structure. The results shown in Table 4 indicate how, in the first four categories, positive linear relations are

obtained between the urban noise and surface area, with explanations for the variability exceeding 78% and even reaching 86%. In addition, there is an increase in the explanation of variability, with respect to 49% of the overall city, in the streets in Category 5, reaching 56%. The results are similar to those found with the population variable. Therefore, the strata structure not only allows a better understanding of the dependence that exists between a city's noise and its surface, but also enables us to describe in detail this dependence according to groups of streets. If a multiple comparison of the variance between the different categories is made using the *F* test, only Category 5 presents significant differences with respect to the rest of the categories as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. *P* values using the *F* test to compare the slopes of the regression lines that are related to the area of the city and the average sound level of the road category

Categories	1	2	3	4
2	0.413	-	-	-
3	0.647	0.709	-	-
4	0.683	0.673	0.961	-
5	0.041	0.006	0.013	0.015

The meaning and relevance of the results with respect to the area variable are considered. First, for this variable, the structure of strata allows a better understanding of the dependence that exists between this structure and a city's noise than the global average level. In addition, the explanations of the variability of the sound level found from the strata structure proposed by the Categorisation Method are similar to those previously found using the population variable. Therefore, they enable the prediction of the dependence between a city's area and the sound level by strata or groups of streets. For this reason, the regression lines in each of the categories are compared.

If the results shown in Table 4 are analysed with respect to the linear relationships and more specifically the slopes of the adjustments, all the values are relatively close. Each

1 time the urban area increases by an order of magnitude, the level increases by 4.1 dBA
2 for Category 5 and approximately 4.5 dBA for Categories 1, 2, and 3, with very similar
3 values. Category 4 experienced the greatest growth in the variable area, with a value of
4 5.4 dBA for an order of magnitude increase in the surface area. However, in reality, if the
5 slopes of the regression lines are compared via an ANCOVA using the F test, a p value
6 > 0.05 is obtained. There are no significant differences between the different slopes of the
7 regression lines obtained in each category. This implies that the increase in the noise level
8 with a city's surface is statistically similar in the different groups of streets. These slope
9 values, when compared with the population variable's values, seem to indicate the
10 importance of urban growth models on the noise level of a city. However, if the values
11 obtained for the ordinate at the origin are analysed according to the categories, their value
12 increases as greater use categories are considered. Its value increases from 55 dBA for
13 Category 5 to 68 dBA for Category 1, which gives a base sound level value for human
14 agglomerations with a reference surface of 1 km² that oscillates between these two values
15 depending on the type of street considered. If the intercepts are analysed using the F test,
16 for any pair of categories compared (p value < 0.001), the intercepts of all of the
17 categories significantly differ. Therefore, similar to the results found with the variable
18 population, with the variable area, the lines found for the categories are also statistically
19 different. As with the variable population, the variable area allows, at least in the range
20 of cities studied with a factor of 100 on the area, the prediction of the noise level in
21 specific streets of a city, with uncertainties that are approximately 1.2 to 2.2 dBA of
22 typical errors.

3.1.3 Dependence of the city's sound level on the total length of its streets

23 In the previous sections, it was proven that the population or area of a city are determining
24 size variables to explain the variability of the sound level in the streets of a city. However,

1 if the urban structure of streets varies or there is a different length of urban roads for
 2 similar population sizes and areas, the sound level in the streets may vary between cities.
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 4 For example, shorter lengths could mean more vehicle density on the streets and
 5 consequently higher noise levels or vice versa. In addition, it is clear that the total length
 6 of the streets in a city, although not commonly used, is an indicator of its size and, in this
 7 sense, it can be expected that significant relationships will be obtained between a city's
 8 sound level and the length of its streets. Figure 4 shows a representation of the dependence
 9 of the sound level with the length of the streets in the cities studied and the regression
 10 lines. The different parameters obtained in the analysis of the linear regression are
 11 presented in Table 6.

Figure 4. Scatter diagrams and regression lines of the sound level in relation to the total length of the streets.

Table 6. Linear regression parameters between the sound level and street length

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log ₁₀ (street length)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	5.568	44.703	0.748	< 0.001	1.521
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	5.572	42.444	0.783	< 0.001	1.378
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	5.994	38.215	0.812	< 0.001	1.357
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	6.756	31.020	0.839	< 0.001	1.398
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	4.958	33.946	0.518	< 0.001	2.255
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	3.836	42.702	0.414	< 0.001	2.149

Table 6 shows that all the relationships between the independent and dependent variables are highly significant (p value < 0.001). In a city's overall sound level, the variable length can explain 41% of the variations in the city's average sound level. The result is lower than those found in the previous sections for the population and area variables. If the dependence of the sound level of a city's streets on the urban structure is studied, the results shown in Table 6 indicate how, in the first four categories, the increase in noise depends on the increase in the street lengths, explaining between approximately 75% and 84% of the variability. The results, while slightly lower than those obtained with the area variable, are similar to those found for the population variable. In the Category 5 streets, a 52% variability was explained. Therefore, for all the strata, in this case the variable length, which is essential for the Categorisation Method, the strata explain the variability of noise in a city better than if the noise was studied globally. For the variable area, Category 5 presents a significantly different variance than the other categories as shown in Table 7. Consequently, the variable length, in the same way as the population and area variables, allows detailing the dependence between urban noise and the different street categories, finding high explanations for the variability.

Table 7. *P* values using the *F* test to compare the slopes of the regression lines that are related to the total length of the city's streets and the road category's average sound level

Categories	1	2	3	4
2	0.637	-	-	-
3	0.573	0.937	-	-
4	0.675	0.949	0.884	-
5	0.044	0.020	0.014	0.020

The results of the linear relationship shown in Table 6 are analysed. The slope values demonstrate that each time the length of urban roads increases by an order of magnitude, the level increases depending on the type of street. A value of 5.0 dBA was obtained for Category 5 and approximately 5.8 dBA for Categories, 1, 2, and 3, very similar values. Category 4 experiences the greatest growth in length, with a value of 6.8 dBA. Despite this apparent difference between the slopes, an analysis of the covariance using the *F* test indicates that they are statistically indistinguishable (*p* value = 0.448). This result is similar to that found with the other two size variables. Greater slopes are obtained than with the other two variables, population and area, which must be associated with the smaller range of the variable length with respect to the ranges of the other two size variables, a factor of 55. If the ordinate's behaviour at the origin for the different categories is studied, its value is significantly higher as categories of greater use (*p* value < 0.001 according to the *F* test) are considered, although there is a slight inversion between Categories 4 and 5. The values range from 31 dBA for Category 4, to 34 dBA for Category 5, and 45 dBA for Category 1. This gives a base value for the sound level for human agglomerations that varies between these two values depending on the type of street that is considered. All the values are very low, which is related to a greater number of orders of magnitude until reaching the zero order of the variable represented. In fact, in Categories 4 and 5, it could be considered a base level in the absence of people, given that it corresponds to the reference of 1 m in length of the city's streets.

1 The stratification of urban roads according to their functionality is a useful tool for urban
2 planners to estimate noise values using variables such as population, area and street
3 length. Cities will continue to grow in the coming years and it is important to estimate the
4 possible effects on the sound environment. Area and population are the variables that
5 explain the greatest variability in sound levels on main streets (Categories 1 to 3) and
6 residential streets (Category 4 and 5), respectively. Considering that Categories 1 to 3
7 correspond to the streets more commonly used by citizens, this result may indicate that
8 the area occupied by the city is an influential factor in the need for vehicle use from
9 residential areas. This is not the case for categories 4 and 5, which are more influenced
10 by the increase in population in residential areas as the city grows. However, these
11 differences in the explanation of variability are not significant between the population,
12 surface area and street length variables. Therefore, any of these variables can be used as
13 predictors of noise levels with relatively low uncertainties.

3.2 Sound level and variables related to population densities

34 Population density is traditionally associated with the population in a given environment
35 relative to that environment's area. In this work, for reasons that will be explained, this
36 variable is called surface density (SD). However, as already indicated, this study is based
37 on the Categorisation Method, which helps explore new possibilities to ascertain the
38 relationship between sound level and population density. In particular, a city's population
39 with respect to the length of its streets was also studied. This variable is called linear
40 density (LD). Therefore, in this section, two types of population density were considered:
41 density per unit area (SD) and density per unit length (LD).

42 As shown in Section 3.1, the population, area, and length variables from which these two
43 new variables (SD and LD) are obtained lead to a positive linear relationship for the sound

1 level in the streets. The three size variables are closely related to each other. Therefore, it
2 is mathematically difficult to predict what dependency there will be between the sound
3 level and new density variables. In fact, it is not even possible to foresee that any
4 significant dependence will exist.
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10 **3.2.1 Dependence of the city's sound level on the surface population density**

11 The SD variable is complex when it comes to foreseeing what relationship it has with the
12 sound level a city's streets. For similar population values, the higher the city's surface
13 density, the smaller the surface area and, consequently, the less need for vehicle use. Also,
14 more people per unit of surface area may imply a higher noise level. The same type of
15 analysis could be applied considering the surface area constant. Therefore, this is an
16 interesting variable to study. Figure 5 shows the representation of the sound level against
17 the variable density and regression lines obtained. Table 8 presents different parameters
18 obtained in the linear regression analysis.
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Figure 5. Scatter diagrams and sound level regression lines with respect to the surface population density.

Table 8. Linear regression parameters between sound level and population density

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log ₁₀ (population density)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	6.052	48.773	0.126	> 0.05	2.835
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	7.343	41.894	0.190*	< 0.05	2.663
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	6.562	42.415	0.138	> 0.05	2.908
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	9.197	28.933	0.220*	< 0.05	3.070
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	7.804	28.393	0.182*	< 0.05	2.936
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	5.538	40.306	0.123	> 0.05	2.630

According to the results shown in Table 8, not all the relationships studied are significant and none are highly significant. The significant relationships (p value < 0.05) are found for the dependence of the sound level with the surface density in Categories 2, 4, and 5. Both the sound levels in Categories 1 and 3 as well as the overall sound level in the city do not have a significant relationship with the population's surface density. Therefore, the variable SD is clearly much less suitable for studying urban noise than the variables

1 directly related to the city's size. In fact, if the variances obtained for the same road
 2 category between the different urban variables (population, surface area, and length) are
 3 compared using the F test, the results show that, except for Category 5, there are
 4 significant differences between the lines obtained with any of the three size variables and
 5 those obtained with the variable SD (Table 9).
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11 Table 9. P values obtained from the comparison in the same category of the variance of
 12 the regression lines obtained for the population, area, length, and linear density (LD)
 13 variables with respect to the variances of the variable SD using the F test
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Category	Population	Area	Length	LD
1	0.003	< 0.001	0.003	0.005
2	0.002	< 0.001	0.002	0.005
3	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.005
4	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.008
5	0.092	0.127	0.194	0.090

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 30 Surface density significantly explains the variability of sound levels recorded in
 31 Categories 2, 4, and 5 at a percentage between 18% and 22%. This percentage is low and
 32 if the variance of these categories is compared with those that do not show significant
 33 relationships, the results of the F test demonstrate that there are no significant differences
 34 between their variances (p value > 0.05). However, despite the low variability explained
 35 by the surface density, the category structure explains the variability of a city's noise with
 36 its surface density.
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49 3.2.2 Dependence of the city's sound level on its linear population density

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 52 The previous sections demonstrated that the city's population or street lengths determine
 53 the size variables to explain the variability of the sound level in the city's streets. A new
 54 variable of density will be explored in this section. This new variable, as previously
 55 defined, is obtained as the quotient of the city's population between the length of its
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streets, which is called the linear population density (LD). To the best of our knowledge, this variable is seldom used to study urban noise. In this study, LD is a variable that arises naturally given the use of the variable length in the Categorisation Method. Similar to the traditional population density variable (SD), this variable is defined from two variables that present a statistically significant increase in the sound level as the variable increases. However, for similar population sizes, the urban structure of streets can vary or there can be differences in the length of the streets, which can lead to unclear trends in the sound level. However, in turn, the sound level's dependence on this variable can be closely related to urban planning. In principle, the difficulty of predicting the existence of relationships between sound levels and the LD variable is similar to that for the SD variable. The results achieved with this new variable are then analysed. Figure 6 represents the dependence of the sound level with the variable LD and the regression lines. The different parameters obtained in the linear regression analysis are presented in Table 10.

Figure 6. Scatter diagrams and sound level regression lines with respect to the linear population density.

Table 10. Linear regression parameters between the sound level and linear population density (LD)

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Slope coefficient	Intercept coefficient	R^2	F statistic (p value)	Standard error
Log ₁₀ (linear population density)	$L_{Aeq-cat.1}$	9.653	74.628	0.588	< 0.001	1.946
	$L_{Aeq-cat.2}$	9.656	72.485	0.639	< 0.001	1.779
	$L_{Aeq-cat.3}$	10.090	70.339	0.602	< 0.001	1.977
	$L_{Aeq-cat.4}$	12.404	67.555	0.738	< 0.001	1.780
	$L_{Aeq-cat.5}$	10.360	61.115	0.591	< 0.001	2.076
	$L_{Aeq-overall}$	8.662	63.916	0.552	< 0.001	1.879

This variable's result is very interesting, even more so if it is compared with that obtained in the previous section for surface density and if it is taken into account that the two variables from which it is defined have high explanations for the sound level's variability. Table 10 shows that all the relationships are highly significant (p value < 0.001). Moreover, the explanations of the variability although in general somewhat lower than the values obtained for the population or length variables have a value that in all cases exceeds 50%. Therefore, correlation coefficients (R^2) above 0.74 are obtained for all the regression lines. Of note, in addition, as was the case with the population, area, and length variables, the LD variable has a significantly different variance than the SD variable in Categories 1 to 4 (Table 6). First, if the city's overall sound level is considered, the variable LD explains 55% of the variations in a city's average sound level. For the city as a whole, this result is the highest of the variables studied. Therefore, the variable LD seems to be the best variable to use to study a city's average noise. Next, the extent to which this variable is capable of explaining the sound level of each stratum of roads defined by the categorisation method is analysed. Table 10 indicates how the five categories explain the increase in noise by the increase in linear density, with explanations

1 of the variability from 59% (Categories 1 and 5) to 74% in Category 4. Therefore, a
2 variable is obtained that explains the variability of noise in a city for all strata that is better
3 than if the noise is studied globally. Furthermore, the structure of the strata allows, with
4 high explanations of the variability, foreseeing the dependence between a density variable
5 and the sound level by strata or groups of streets. However, if an inferential analysis is
6 conducted using the F test, no statistically significant differences are found in the
7 variances of these regression lines. In addition, as with the size variables, the variable LD
8 has significantly different explanations of the variability than those obtained using the
9 variable SD in all of the categories, except Category 5 (Table 6).
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22 Next, the results shown in Table 10 regarding the linear relationship are analysed. All the
23 slope values are relatively close. Each time a city's linear density increases by an order
24 of magnitude, the sound level increases depending on the type of street by almost 10 dBA
25 for Categories 1, 2, 3, and 5 and 12 dBA for Category 4. However, analysing the
26 covariance using the F test demonstrates that these slopes do not present significant
27 differences (p value = 0.727) and the increase in the sound level by street categories is
28 the same when the variable LD is used. These values of the slopes naturally linked to the
29 variable's small range may indicate that a city's population per unit length of urban roads
30 is an important variable for controlling the city's existing sound level. Analysing the
31 original order shows that its value increases as greater use categories are considered. The
32 values range from 61 dBA for Category 5 to 75 dBA for Category 1. These values also
33 have significant differences according to the F test ($p < 0.001$). These results, which give
34 a base value of the sound level according to the type of street considered, naturally have
35 such high values due to the relationship between the zero value of the LD variable and
36 the structures of the cities. Bear in mind that the zero value corresponds to a linear density
37 of 1 inhabitant for each meter of street. Consequently, most cities have negative variable
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1 LD values. Furthermore, the results show that for this variable, the categories correspond
2 to different sound levels. The new density variable allows the estimation of the sound
3 level by groups of streets with uncertainties in general somewhat greater than those
4 obtained with the size variables. Nevertheless, these are relatively low and very uniform
5 in all of the strata a range of 1.8 to 2.1 dBA with respect to the standard error.
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12 The area, population and street length variables were positively correlated with noise
13 levels. However, there may be differences in the urban planning of the cities studied,
14 despite the relationships between these three variables. In this way, new variables may
15 result from the combination of these variables that may contribute to regulate the increase
16 in noise levels due to future growth of cities. Population density predicted low
17 percentages of sound variability as shown above. This may indicate that urban growth
18 based on higher population densities in cities does not necessarily imply less use of
19 vehicles. However, linear density proved to be a good predictor. Increasing the length of
20 streets for the same population can lead to a decrease in noise levels. Increasing
21 alternative roads or long ring roads does not seem to lead to a substantial increase in car
22 use, but may lead to lower traffic density and improvements in vehicle distribution. In
23 summary, the results show that it is not proven that less dense cities will decrease their
24 noise levels. However, increasing the number of roads for equal population decreases the
25 use per unit length of road.
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47 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

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49 The relationships between urban variables related to the size of a city and noise levels for
50 categories of streets according to their use have been analysed.
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1 The results found indicated that the variables associated to the size of the cities
2 (population, area, street length) explain a higher variability of urban noise when it is
3 analysed by strata. A classification of urban roads according to their functionality is useful
4 in urban planning to significantly stratify urban noise and to establish estimates from
5 urban variables. For the range of cities studied (population from 2,238 to 699,759
6 inhabitant), the population, surface area, and length variables allowed the prediction of
7 the noise level in streets categories with uncertainties of approximately 1.2 to 2.3 dBA.
8 These linear regression models can also help predict noise levels on different road
9 categories for future variations in city size. The noise level increased between 3.6 and 6.8
10 dBA by an order of magnitude depending on the variable and street category. Regarding
11 the road categories, these urban variables explain a greater variability (> 75%) in streets
12 with the highest noise levels (Categories 1 to 4). These urban roads are of greatest interest
13 to city managers because of their greater negative impact on health.

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32 In the variables related to population density, the findings demonstrated that the surface
33 density variable had a low explanation for the variability of sound levels recorded in road
34 categories. However, the linear density variable obtained statistically significant
35 relationships in all of the categories with relatively low and very uniform uncertainties
36 (standard error between 1.8 and 2.1 dBA). In addition, linear density was the best
37 predictor of the overall average level of the city. An increase in the population of a city
38 leads to an increase in noise levels. However, this growth can be compensated by
39 appropriate development of urban roads. In this way, the population will not collapse
40 urban roads and will be able to take alternative roads to reach their destination.

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55 Finally, future lines of research are emerging from the results of this study. Increasing the
56 number of cities could allow to study differences between city types, countries, etc. New
57 variables that consider street lengths according to the Categorisation Method typologies

1 may also allow improvements in the dependence on noise levels and help to better
2 understand the relationships between the urban planning of cities and the noise levels of
3 their streets.
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Author statements

Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Guillermo Rey Gozalo:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Visualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **David Montes González:** Validation, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Rosendo Vílchez-Gómez:** Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Valentín Gómez Escobar:** Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: